

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

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**THE USAGE OF TECHNOLOGIES AND WIKI-TECHNOLOGIES
INTEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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